

BIOREMEDIATION POTENTIAL OF INDIGENOUS MICROORGANISMS ISOLATED FROM THE INDUSTRIAL ZONE OF THE SHARGUN COAL MINE

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Abstract. *Industrial enterprises and coal mining processes pose serious ecological threats to the natural environment. In particular, in the Shargun coal mine area of Surkhandarya region, soil and water resources are contaminated with coal dust, heavy metals, and various toxic substances. This situation leads to a reduction in microbiological diversity, disruption of ecosystems, and a decline in soil fertility. Therefore, studying the biotechnological potential of indigenous microorganisms and developing bioremediation technologies based on them is of great scientific and practical importance.*

Keywords. *Shargun coal mine, indigenous microorganisms, Bacillus simplex, Pseudomonas fluorescens, bioremediation, enzymatic activity, ecological monitoring.*

At the global level, industrial expansion, particularly coal mining, has had severe negative impacts on the environment. In the Shargun coal mine area, the accumulation of coal dust particles, heavy metals, and toxic elements in soils and waters has led to a drastic reduction in biological diversity. This situation necessitates ecological monitoring and bioremediation studies. Hence, the deterioration of soil, water, and air quality in active or abandoned coal mining sites is regarded as one of the major global environmental challenges [1].

A study conducted in Brazil (2015) demonstrated that soil microbial biomass and enzymatic activity decreased significantly after coal extraction, though a tendency toward natural recovery was observed over time. Proteobacteria, Acidobacteria, and Firmicutes were identified as dominant microbial groups, and their imbalance indicated disruption of the microbial community under contamination stress [2].

Zhou et al. (2024) reported the effective bioremediation of heavy metals (Cd and Pb) using *Bacillus pasteurii* and hydrothermal carbon. Within 30 days, the concentrations of Cd and Pb were reduced by 89.4% and 87.8%, respectively. The mechanism was explained by microbially induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP), where carbonate deposits immobilized the heavy metal ions [3].

Unitsky et al. (2022) investigated the microbial solubilization of brown coal as a method for producing humic acids. Strains of *Acinetobacter pittii*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Microbacterium* sp., *Bacillus* sp., and the lignin-degrading fungus *Trametes versicolor* were tested. Coal concentrations of 0.5–5.0% were used to evaluate solubilization efficiency. *Bacillus* sp. and *Enterobacter cloacae* showed active growth in 5% coal medium, while humic acid yields increased threefold under the influence of *Trametes versicolor*. These results highlight the dual

stages of microbial bioconversion—depolymerization of organic matter into soluble fractions and their incorporation into metabolism—with key roles played by lignin peroxidase, laccases, and Mn-peroxidase [5].

The main objective of this study was to identify microorganisms isolated from the industrial zone of the Shargun coal mine, to investigate their physiological, biochemical, and enzymatic properties, and to evaluate their bioremediation potential in mitigating industrial pollution.

A total of five samples (soil, water, coal, and waste storage sites) were collected from the industrial area. Soil samples were taken from depths of 0–5, 5–15, and 15–30 cm using a stratified approach. Samples were processed under sterile conditions and inoculated onto Nutrient Agar and Czapek Agar media. The resulting colonies were identified using MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry.

The physiological properties of the isolates were assessed in mineral medium supplemented with 1% coal, with sucrose medium used as a control. Experiments were carried out at 37°C, with shaking at 160 rpm for 120 hours. Enzymatic activity was determined using Raymond mineral medium supplemented with starch, cellulose, and tannin.

Results. More than 20 isolates were obtained from soil and water sources, and they were identified as belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Glutamicibacter*, *Kocuria*, *Acinetobacter*, and *Mycobacterium*. The highest microbial density was recorded in soil samples collected at the mine entrance (5.75×10^7 CFU/g).

After 120 hours of incubation in coal medium, the following results were obtained:

- *Pseudomonas fluorescens* – 2.8×10^6 cells/mL;
- *Bacillus simplex* – 2.7×10^6 cells/mL;
- *Bacillus subtilis* – 2.5×10^6 cells/mL;
- *Kocuria rosea* – the leading strain in protein synthesis (1.10 mg/mL).

Enzymatic activity analyses revealed that:

- In starch medium, *Glutamicibacter arilaitensis* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* exhibited the highest activity.
- In cellulose medium, *Bacillus simplex* and *Bacillus subtilis* demonstrated strong hydrolytic activity.
- In tannin medium, *Kocuria rosea* and *Bacillus subtilis* showed superior performance.

For all strains, the pH of the culture medium remained within the range of 6.85–7.12, indicating stable adaptation to the substrate.

Discussion. The obtained results confirmed that indigenous microorganisms possess a high capacity to degrade various organic biopolymers (starch, cellulose, tannin). Among them, *Bacillus simplex* demonstrated superior cell density, enzymatic activity, and metabolic stability, suggesting its potential application as a promising bioremediation agent in environments contaminated with industrial waste.

In parallel, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* exhibited rapid growth and strong substrate utilization capacity, indicating its important role in bioremediation processes. Additionally, the isolation of *Glutamicibacter arilaitensis* from different water sources revealed its high ecological adaptability.

When compared with findings from international literature (Zhou et al., 2024; Unitsky et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2023), the results align with global trends confirming the ability of *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* species to bioconvert coal, immobilize heavy metals, and contribute to dust cementation.

Conclusion. Indigenous strains isolated from the Shargun coal mine—*Bacillus simplex*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Pseudomonas fluorescens*—demonstrated strong ecological adaptability and bioremediation potential. These strains are recommended as valuable resources for industrial waste biotransformation, humic acid production, and the restoration of polluted soil–water ecosystems. In future studies, the development of biopreparations based on these strains and the evaluation of their efficiency under field conditions are planned.

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